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Original Research Article

Development of a new isolation technique and validated RP-HPLC method for Quercetin and Kaempferol from *Camellia sinensis* leaves.Sudhakar Chavراسiya^{1*}, Narendra Pratap Singh Sengar¹, PD Mehta¹, J Banweer, Swapna Sahu².¹Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Sagar Institute of Research & Technology-Pharmacy, SAGE University, Bhopal, M.P., India.²Faculty of Pharmacy, Nirmala Devi Pharmacy College, Gaurabadshahpur, Jaunpur, U.P., India.

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received : 10-Oct-2022 Revised : 25-Oct-2022 Accepted : 10-Nov-2022</p>	<p>Aim and Objective: The purpose of this study was to create a new approach for separating the two main flavonoids, quercetin and kaempferol, from <i>Camellia Sinensis</i> leave using the RP-HPLC method.</p>
<p>Key words</p> <p>Quercetin, Kaempferol, <i>Camellia sinensis</i>, RP-HPLC, Flavonoid, Phenolic.</p>	<p>Materials & Methods: The preparative column was used to isolate the flavonoids after the analytical column had first separated and identified them. A third-party, industry-standard analytical RP-HPLC technique was used to determine the presence of quercetin and kaempferol. The software was used to set up the fraction collection, and the chromatogram's peak times for quercetin (7.42 min) and kaempferol (11.39 min) were recorded.</p>
<p>NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International License (CC BY-NC-SA)</p>	<p>Results: For quercetin and kaempferol, respectively, the UV area% purity of the obtained components was 86.67 and 89.23. The maximum emission wavelengths of isolated quercetin and conventional quercetin were 256 nm and 365 nm, respectively. The maximum and minimum wavelengths of isolated kaempferol were 259 nm and 361 nm, respectively, as opposed to 267 nm and 368 nm for conventional kaempferol. The FT-IR spectra of quercetin and kaempferol (both standard and isolated) overlap. Indicating -OH groups, the major spectral peaks were seen at >3300 cm⁻¹ and 1600–1700 cm⁻¹ (representing the carbonyl function).</p> <p>Conclusion: It has been discovered that the technique is exact, accurate, linear, durable, cost-effective, sensitive, and capable of quickly isolating both of the essential phytoconstituents from the extracted natural materials. The study thus opens up possibilities for using this technology in industry-based activities and quality control procedures at various operability scales.</p>
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INTRODUCTION

The phenolic chemicals are significant secondary plant metabolites with a wide range of biological and pharmacological effects, including anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, anti-viral, anti-ulcer, anti-allergenic, and anti-inflammatory properties [1-4]. Additionally, these substances seem to have some anti-cancer and anti-cardiovascular effects. In order to preserve food for organoleptic and nutritional values, phenolic compounds are also used as a natural antioxidant or as a food additive [6-7].

Flavonoids are one of the important and largest classes of phenolic compounds, generally known to be present in plant and plant-based products, associated with a broad spectrum of health-promoting effects [8]. The presence and concentration of these compounds vary even in the same plant at different ripening stages and organs of the same plant. Some plants are found to be excellent sources of phenolic compounds and are suggested to use for the preservation of food as well as to get health benefits [9]. Quercetin and kaempferol

(Figure 1) are the basic flavonoids that possess anti-oxidant, anti-microbial, antiviral, anti-mutagenic, and anti-inflammatory properties [10].

Quercetin

Kaempferol

Figure 1. Structure of the phytoconstituents.

Camellia Sinensis (*A. indica*) known by the Hindi name Neem, is a member of the mahogany family *Meliaceae* [11-12]. Different parts (roots, stem, bark, leaves, flower, fruits, and seeds) of *A. indica* have been used traditionally for the treatment of infections, inflammation, fever, dental disorders, and skin diseases [3-15]. More than 140 active chemicals, including phenolic compounds, alkaloids, triterpenoids, flavonoids, carotenoids, ketones, and steroids, have been identified from *A. indica* [16-19].

The aim of this study was to isolate the two major flavonoids, quercetin and kaempferol by using the RP-HPLC technique from *A. indica* leaves by establishing a new method and also to recognize the critical parameters essentially required for the identification. The preparative column was used to isolate the flavonoids after the analytical column had first separated and identified them..

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Instrumentation

The RP-HPLC system comprised of Shimadzu® LC-2010 CHT (Kyoto, Japan) with an inbuilt SPD 20-AD UV-Vis detector. The separation was carried out by using reverse-phase column Intersil ODS-3 C-18 (5 μ m, 4.6 mm $\times$ 250 mm). The UV-spectrophotometric

analysis was performed using the double-beam Shimadzu® Ultraviolet-Visible Spectrophotometer (Kyoto, Japan) of model UV-1800 which is equipped with a pair of 1 cm path length quartz cells. The weighing applications were carried out on Shimadzu® AUW220D balance. The pH was determined by utilizing Contech® digital pH meter. The sonication was done with a sonicator of the Transonic Digital S model (USA).

Collection of plant

The *A. indica* was collected from the local area of Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India. During the month of January, the newly fully green leaves at the beginning of maturity were chosen. The Department of Pharmacognosy properly authenticated the plant, and it was subsequently delivered to the Institutional Museum for preservation. All of the sample leaves were thoroughly wetted before being dried in a vacuum oven for 48 hours at 40°C. Using a professional grinder and an 80-mesh sieve, the dry leaves were ground into powder. The powder sample was kept for further analysis in the polyethylene bags in the desiccating cabinet.

Preparation of extract

200 cc of distilled water were macerated with 20 g of dried leaves. To get rid of the fatty components, 50 ml of petroleum ether was used to fractionate the aqueous extract. The aqueous extract was subsequently extracted with 50 ml of ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract was dried over anhydrous H₂SO₄ and evaporated to dryness under N₂ stream at 40°C.

Study and selection of wavelength

The solutions of the standard phytoconstituents at a concentration of 10 μ g/mL were scanned in the range of 400-200 nm in a 1 cm cell against blank sample using UV-Vis spectrophotometer in a triplicate manner to accurately measure the λ_{max} and the mean was reported. It was discovered that the wavelengths of the spectrum used to identify the phytoconstituents were 364 nm for quercetin and 368 nm for kaempferol. The most common wavelength employed for the detection was 366 nm.

Preparation of standard solution

1 mg of both the standard phytoconstituents was transferred into separate 100 mL of volumetric and

suitably diluted with acetonitrile and further sonicated to completely dissolve the substances. The final volume was made up to 10 µg/mL after cooling the solution to room temperature.

Characterization of quercetin and kaempferol by RP-HPLC

The two flavonoids were separated by analytical column Intersil ODS-3 C-18 (5 µm, 4.6 mm × 250 mm) using mobile phase acetonitrile: methanol: aqueous solution of 0.2% formic acid in a ratio of 60:10:30 at a flow rate of 1 ml/min in the total run time of 20 min at the isocratic mode by using UV-Vis detector.

Isolation of quercetin and kaempferol by RP-HPLC

The obtained extract was sonicated for the duration of 20 min in a sonicator and the sonicated extract was passed through the ultra-membrane filter (pore size 0.45 µm) prior to injection in the sample loop. The obtained filtrate was thoroughly analyzed by the HPLC system. The scaled preparative chromatographic method could gather the peak of interest, just like the analytical method. The quercetin and kaempferol were isolated and achieved by semi-preparative column Intersil ODS-3 C-18 (5 µm, 6 mm × 250 mm), using mobile phase composition; acetonitrile: methanol: aqueous solution of 0.2% formic acid in a ratio of 60:10:30 at isocratic mode. The selection of the mobile phase was decisive and subsequently, numerous trials with the solvent mixtures, the critical parameters like degree of separation between the two components, the best possible symmetry of the obtained peaks, index of peak purity, and the number of theoretical plates covered were taken into account for choosing the best mobile phase. The acceptable preparative separation was achieved using a 20 µl injection. 10 ml/min was chosen as the flow rate.

Validation of method

For estimating the linearity, different concentrations were selected at ranges of 25-150% of the target analyte concentrations. An equivalent amount of each solution was analyzed by chromatography and the obtained calibration graph (average area versus concentration) was plotted to determine the regression coefficient value (r^2) [20]. The recovery

was determined by spiking the phytoconstituents in a placebo at a fixed concentration along with the placebo amount in the chromatography system. The % recovery, % means, and % relative standard deviation (RSD) values were determined and expressed [21]. The variability between and among days was used to examine the method's accuracy. The intra-day analysis was executed at three concentrations of the standard solution on a single day (intra-day) and on a three-difference day (inter-day) [22]. The robustness of the method was studied and the effect of changing the flow rate by the value of + 0.2 mL/min; i.e. 1.2 mL/min and wavelength by +2 nm (now 368 nm) while keeping the other chromatographic conditions stable [23]. All the experimental studies were done in a triplicate manner and the obtained mean was reported.

Spectrophotometric analysis

The isolated phytoconstituents were dissolved in methanol and λ_{max} was determined by UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu® UV-1800, Japan) by scanning over the wavelength of 200 to 400 nm. The obtained peak(s) were compared with the standard quercetin and kaempferol. In addition to it, the Fourier-transformed Infrared Spectroscopy spectra (Shimadzu® IRAffinity-1, Japan) of the isolated phytoconstituents were determined using the KBr method and compared with the standard.

Data analysis

The retention time(s) and concentration(s) of phenolic acid were identified by using HPLC software (Cyberlab-Chrom HPLC).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isolation of quercetin and kaempferol

The previously reported literature revealed the utility of C8 and C18 columns of the dimension (250 × 4.5 mm i.d., 1.7 or 5 µm particle size) for the resolution of both of these phytoconstituents, therefore, in this study reverse-phase column Intersil ODS-3 C-18 (5 µm, 4.6 mm × 250 mm) was employed. To accomplish the best separation and isolation of these two prime substituents, the composition, type, pH, and formulation of the mobile phase played a critical function.

Figure 2. RP-HPLC Chromatogram of Identification Quercetin and Kaempferol.

Figure 3. RP-HPLC Chromatogram of Isolation of Quercetin and Kaempferol.

Table 1. Recovery for accuracy studies.

Phytoconstituent	Content taken	Amount added to placebo	Amount recovered	% recovery	% mean	% RSD
Quercetin	10	10	19.86	99.3	99.93	1.11
	10	10	20.19	100.95		
	10	10	19.91	99.55	99.88	1.17
	10	15	25.17	100.68		
	10	15	24.85	99.4		
	10	15	24.89	99.56		
	10	20	30.11	100.36	99.87	1.04
	10	20	29.90	99.66		
10	20	29.88	99.6			
Kaempferol	10	10	19.94	99.7	99.65	1.09
	10	10	19.99	99.95		
	10	10	19.86	99.3	100.30	0.91
	10	15	24.93	99.72		
	10	15	25.13	100.52		
	10	15	25.17	100.68		
	10	20	29.96	99.86	99.73	1.29
	10	20	29.82	99.4		
10	20	29.98	99.93			

Table 2. Precision and repeatability of the phytoconstituents.

Phytoconstituent	Equivalent amount taken	Amount determined (Inter-day)	% RSD	Amount determined (Intra-day)	% RSD
Quercetin	10	9.89	0.87	10.03	0.99
	10	10.14		9.81	
	10	9.95		9.92	
	25	24.79	1.16	25.12	1.14
		24.97		24.90	
		24.86		25.06	
	50	49.94	1.22	50.02	1.13
		49.88		49.93	
		49.85		50.16	
Kaempferol	10	9.92	0.82	9.95	1.01
	10	9.96		10.07	
	10	9.90		9.99	
	25	24.93	1.11	24.99	1.18
		24.89		24.97	
		24.81		24.85	
	50	49.91	1.19	49.80	1.07
		49.84		50.05	
		49.98		49.91	

The selection was solely based on peak symmetry, theoretical plate, and peak purity index, and numerous trials were conducted using multiple solvent systems such as water, methanol, acetonitrile, and various buffers of pH 3.0-6.0. An optimized pH of the mobile phase was maintained to prevent the tailing and dissolution of the silica of the column. An external standard analytical RP-HPLC approach was used to identify the quercetin and kaempferol, and the standard characterization method reflected the typical peaks of the two compounds (Figure 2). The fraction collection was set up through software and the peaks collected in the chromatogram were 7.42 min for quercetin and 11.39 for kaempferol (Figure 3). The purity of the collected compounds showed UV area % purity of 86.67 and 89.23 for quercetin and kaempferol, respectively. The tailing factor (TF) of both the peaks averagely remained near unity which expressed excellent peak symmetry and the asymmetric factor (AF) is nearly or equal to 1, as with the enhancement in the AF, the phenomenon of tailing becomes prominent. As per the analytical observations, TF value < 2 represents the ideal Gaussian peak [21].

Validation

Both phytochemical samples' linearity expressions were discovered to be within the permitted range. The values of the regression coefficients were greater than 0.99, indicating the desired degree of linearity.

The calibration curve was used to determine the recovery of the two compounds. The estimated % RSD values were noticed to be < 2% in each case which described that the values were within the acceptable limit (Table 1). Thus, the newly developed analytical method for the estimation of quercetin and kaempferol has good accuracy. The precision data representing the intra-day and inter-day variability are described in Table 2. The % RSD values were noticed < 2% in each case which depicted that the newly developed method was quite specific for the estimation of the phytoconstituents. The distinction between the intra-day and inter-day variability was perceived to be fairly nominal and also within the range. With the alteration in the chromatographic conditions, a very minute, but deliberate change was observed. The Rt values of quercetin and kaempferol shifted to 7.48 min and 11.46 min, respectively, when the flow rate was modified to 1.2 mL/min. Additionally, when the detection wavelength was changed by 2 nm, the observed Rt values were 7.46 and 11.44 minutes, respectively, demonstrating the method's resilience.

Spectrophotometric analysis

The maximum emission wavelengths of isolated quercetin and conventional quercetin were 256 nm and 365 nm, respectively. The maximum and minimum wavelengths of isolated kaempferol were 259 nm and 361 nm, respectively, compared to 267

nm and 368 nm for conventional kaempferol. These findings suggested that flavonoid structure existed. The π - π^* transitions in the aromatic system (ring A) are where the main absorption came from, and the cinnamoyl system is where the secondary absorption may have arisen (ring B). Because the second band and the LMCT band overlapped, it gave the impression of being wider. Additionally, the FT-IR spectra of kaempferol and quercetin (both isolated and standard) superimpose on one another. The major spectral peaks were found at $>3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which denoted -OH groups, and $1600\text{--}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (representing the carbonyl function) [24].

CONCLUSION

The current study uses the RP-HPLC method to isolate the two most significant medicinal natural products—quercetin and kaempferol—from the *Camellia Sinensis* plant. This technology has been updated and is commercially exploitable. It has been discovered that the technique is exact, accurate, linear, durable, cost-effective, sensitive, and capable of quickly isolating both of the important phytoconstituents from the extracted natural materials. The study thus opens up possibilities for using this technology in industry-based activities and quality control procedures at various operability scales. For the still superior chromatographic approach to isolate and characterize flavonoids from plant extracts more quickly, more research is required.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared.

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